

Studies on the Use of Acetothioacetanilide as a Gravimetric Reagent for Zinc, Cadmium and Mercury

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Zinc (8-33 mg), cadmium (10-30 mg) and mercury(II) (18-54 mg) have been determined by weighing their *bis*-complexes with acetothioacetanilide of general formula $M(C_{10}H_{10}ONS)_2$, M standing for Zn, Cd or Hg. The ranges of complete precipitation are 7.0-7.5, 6.9-8.7 and 1.3-1.8 respectively. Separation of Cd^{2+} from Zn^{2+} is possible in the presence of citrate, from Pb^{2+} in the presence of triethanolamine and from Mg^{2+} , UO_2^{2+} , Cr^{3+} and Al^{3+} in the presence of tartrate. Mercury(II) can be separated from Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , MoO_4^{2-} , Sb^{3+} , Bi^{3+} , Fe^{3+} , Cr^{3+} , Th^{4+} , Zr^{4+} , VO^{2+} , VO_2^+ , MoO_4^{2-} and TeO_4^{2-} when sufficient Na_2 -EDTA is added. Tartrate can also be used to mask Fe^{3+} , while Pb^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Mg^{2+} and Al^{3+} do not interfere at the pH of precipitation of mercury(II). Cadmium and mercury(II) have also been separated by controlling the pH. Only AsO_4^{3-} has been found not to interfere with the determination of zinc. However, the zinc content of several samples of non-ferrous alloys have been determined after separating the foreign ions using an anion exchanger, Dowex-50-WX8 (Cl^-). The relative standard deviations are $\pm 0.5\%$, $\pm 0.31\%$ and $\pm 0.14\%$ respectively for zinc, cadmium and mercury(II).

ZINC(II), cadmium(II) and mercury(II) prefer polarisable ligands due to their 'softness'. However, mercury(II) has the greatest cation deformability among these ions. Thus it is not surprising to find more organic ligands forming thermally stable chelates with mercury(II) in comparison to zinc(II) or cadmium(II).

Although quinoxaline-2-carboxylic acid and its derivatives¹ have been recommended for the gravimetric determination of zinc, they are of limited use due to poor selectivity. The thiourea-Reinecke's salt method^{2,3} is still used widely for the determination of cadmium as the other organic precipitants recommended, viz. 2-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)-benzoxazole⁴, 1-phenyl-tetrazoline-5-thione⁵ and 1-immino-3-thioisindoline⁶ have low selectivity. Only N-phenylbenzohydroxamic acid⁷ appears to have good selectivity in acetate medium. Mercury(II) on the other hand has been determined using precipitants containing nitrogen and sulphur⁸⁻¹⁴ as well as oxygen¹⁵⁻²⁰.

Acetothioacetanilide, $CH_3COCH_2CSNHC_6H_5$ having coordination sites at one oxygen and one sulphur atoms has been used in this investigation for the direct gravimetric determination of zinc(II), cadmium(II) and mercury(II). All the complexes have metal to ligand ratio 1 : 2 and the relative stabilities are in the order of $Hg > Cd > Zn$. Thus, mercury(II) has been separated from a number of diverse ions by masking them, while the scope of using such sequestering agents decreases in case of cadmium or zinc. Zinc has been determined in several samples of brass and other alloys.

Experimental

Acetothioacetanilide solution: The reagent was prepared following the method of Barnikow, Kunzek and Richter²¹. A 1.4% solution of the reagent in 50-(0% ethanol was prepared.

Standard zinc solution: A stock solution was prepared by dissolving metallic zinc (G.R., E.Merck) in dilute hydrochloric acid. The metal content was estimated by titration with Na_2 -EDTA²².

Standard cadmium solution: Hydrated cadmium sulphate (G.R., E.Merck) was dissolved in dilute sulphuric acid and the cadmium content was determined by the thiourea Reinecke's salt method²³.

Standard mercury(II) solution: Mercuric chloride (G.R., E.Merck) was dissolved in dilute nitric acid and the metal content was determined gravimetrically with benzoyl-*m*-nitroacetanilide²⁴.

Diverse ions: Stock solutions were prepared from pure samples of nitrates, chlorides and sulphates of various metal ions.

Apparatus: A Cambridge pH Meter and a photo-recording Metriplex Derivatograph OD-102 (Hungary) were used.

Procedure for zinc: Dilute a known quantity of zinc solution containing 8-33 mg of zinc to 150 ml and add 1 g of sodium chloride. Raise the pH to above 6.0 with dilute ammonia (1M) and warm slightly

(30-35°). Add the reagent (0.30-0.35 g) solution with stirring and adjust the pH between 7.0-7.5 with aqueous ammonia (1M). Digest the complex formed on a hot (40°) water-bath for about 30 min. Filter the white precipitate, wash with water at room temperature and dry at about 100-95°. Calculate the zinc content using a factor of 0.1453.

Procedure for cadmium: Dilute the solution containing 10-30 mg of cadmium to 150 ml, adjust the pH to 5.0-6.0 with aqueous ammonia (2M) and heat to 70-80° after adding 1-2 g of sodium chloride. Add 13-15 ml of the reagent (0.18-0.21 g) solution with stirring. Raise the pH to 7.5-8.0 with aqueous triethanolamine (20%) or ammonia (1M). Allow the lemon-yellow voluminous precipitate to cool down (~20°) by placing in a water-bath. Filter through a sintered glass crucible of fine porosity, wash the cold water and dry at 100°. Use 0.2262 as the factor for determining the cadmium content.

When cadmium was precipitated in the presence of foreign ions, the appropriate masking agent was added before the reagent.

Procedure for mercury(II): Dilute an aliquot of the mercury solution containing 18-54 mg of the metal to 150 ml and adjust the pH to 1.3-1.8 using dilute nitric acid. Add 5-10 ml of the reagent (0.07-0.14 g) solution with stirring. Leave the mixture on a hot water-bath for about 20 min and stir occasionally. Filter, wash with hot (70-80°) water and dry at 120°. The conversion factor is 0.3429.

In order to effect separation of mercury(II) from foreign ions Na₂-EDTA was added before adding the reagent.

The results of the determination of all the three metals are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF ZINC, CADMIUM AND MERCURY

Metal taken (mg)	Wt. of ppt. (mg)	Metal found (mg)	Rel. error (%)
Zn ²⁺ 32.7	225.4, 225.1	32.8, 32.7	0.03, nil
Zn ²⁺ 16.4	112.6, 112.5	16.4, 16.4	nil, nil
Zn ²⁺ 8.2	56.3, 56.3	8.2, 8.2	nil, nil
Cd ²⁺ 34.0	150.0, 150.0	33.93, 34.0	-0.20, nil
Cd ²⁺ 28.3	124.9, 124.8	28.2, 28.2	+0.35, +0.35
Cd ²⁺ 22.6	100.4, 100.2	22.7, 22.7	+0.44, +0.44
Hg ²⁺ 54.5	156.4, 156.6	53.6, 53.7	-0.18, -0.36
Hg ²⁺ 36.3	106.0, 106.1	36.3, 36.3	nil, nil
Hg ²⁺ 18.2	52.5, 53.0	18.0, 18.1	-1.09, -0.54

Results

The nature of the complexes: The colour of the complexes changed from very pale yellow to yellow in the order zinc, cadmium and mercury. The solubility in ethanol (95%) increased in the reverse order though it was very low in dilute alcohol in all the cases.

Mercury(II)-bis-acetothioacetanilide complex when precipitated from solutions at 30° was yellow in colour and was moderately soluble in ethanol, though the solubility was low in acetone, chloroform or isobutylmethyl ketone. The complex was yellow when dried at 90-95° but turned greenish above 100°. On boiling the freshly precipitated complex for some time it turned black slowly.

TABLE 2 -DETERMINATION OF CADMIUM IN PRESENCE OF DIVERSE IONS, Cd (II) TAKEN=28.3 mg.

Diverse ion (mg)	Condition	Wt. of complex (mg)	Cd ²⁺ found (mg)	Rel. error (%)
Zn ²⁺ , 100	a	125.9, 125.5	28.5, 28.4	+0.70, +0.35
Pb ²⁺ , 100	b	125.8, 126.0	28.4, 28.5	+0.35, +0.70
Mg ²⁺ , 100	c	126.0, 125.2	28.5, 28.3	+0.70, nil
Hg ²⁺ , 100	d	124.9, 125.0	28.2, 28.3	-0.35, nil
UO ₂ ²⁺ , 100	c	124.8, 126.0	28.2, 28.5	-0.35, +0.70
Cr ³⁺ , 100	c	124.8, 125.1	28.2, 28.3	-0.35, nil
Al ³⁺ , 100	c	125.1, 125.2	28.3, 28.3	nil, nil
In ²⁺ , 100	c	125.6, 125.4	28.4, 28.4	+0.35, +0.35

(a) Citrate added
(c) Tartrate added

(b) Triethanol amine added
(d) pH separation.

TABLE 3—D.TERMINATION OF MERCURY (II) IN PRESENCE OF DIVERSE IONS, Hg (II) TAKEN=36.3 mg.

Diverse ion (mg)	Masking agent	Wt. of complex (mg)	Hg (II) found (mg)	Rel. error (%)
Zn ²⁺ , 100	a	105.9, 106.0	36.3, 36.3	nil , nil
Cd ²⁺ , 100	a	106.1, 106.1	36.4, 36.4	+0.27, +0.27
Cu ²⁺ , 100	a	106.1, 106.0	36.4, 36.3	+0.27, nil
Pb ²⁺ , 100	—	106.0, 106.0	36.3, 36.3	nil , nil
Ni ²⁺ , 100	a	106.0, 106.1	36.3, 36.4	nil , +0.27
Co ²⁺ , 100	a	106.1, 105.9	36.4, 36.3	+0.27, nil
Mn ²⁺ , 100	—	105.9, 105.8	36.3, 36.2	nil , -0.27
Mg ²⁺ , 100	—	106.0, 106.0	36.3, 36.3	nil , nil
Be ²⁺ , 100	—	106.1, 106.0	36.4, 36.3	+0.27, nil
VO ²⁺ , 100	—	106.1, 106.1	36.4, 36.4	+0.27, +0.27
VO ₂ ³⁺ , 100	a	106.0, 106.1	36.3, 36.4	nil , +0.27
MoO ₄ ²⁻ , 100	a	105.8, 105.9	36.2, 36.3	-0.27, nil
Sb ³⁺ , 100	a	105.9, 105.9	36.3, 36.3	nil , nil
Bi ³⁺ , 100	a	106.0, 106.1	36.3, 36.4	nil , +0.27
Fe ³⁺ , 100	a	106.1, 105.9	36.4, 36.3	+0.27, nil
Fe ²⁺ , 100	b	105.9, 105.8	36.3, 36.2	nil , -0.27
Al ³⁺ , 100	—	106.0, 105.8	36.3, 36.2	nil , -0.27
Cr ³⁺ , 100	a	106.0, 106.0	36.3, 36.3	nil , nil
Tl ¹⁺ , 100	a	106.0, 106.0	36.3, 36.3	nil , nil
Zr ⁴⁺ , 100	a	105.8, 106.0	36.2, 36.3	-0.27, nil
Ce ⁴⁺ , 100	a	106.0, 105.8	36.3, 36.2	nil , -0.27
VO ₂ ⁻ , 100	a	106.1, 105.9	36.4, 36.3	+0.27, nil
MoO ₄ ²⁻ , 100	a	106.1, 105.9	36.4, 36.3	+0.27, nil
TeO ₄ ²⁻ , 100	a	106.0, 106.0	36.3, 36.3	nil , nil

(a) Na₂-EDTA, (b) Na-K tartrate.

Samples of pure complexes were analysed for nitrogen by Kjeldahl's (micro) method and for sulphur by conversion to sulphate. The metal contents were also determined in case of zinc and cadmium after decomposing the ligand. The experimental

Reqd. for M(C ₁₀ H ₁₀ ONS) ₂ , %	Found, %
Zn, 14.53; N, 6.23; S, 14.23	Zn, 14.44; N, 6.11; S, 14.11
Cd, 22.62; N, 5.64; S, 12.90	Cd, 22.52; N, 5.71; S, 13.19
Hg, 34.29; N, 4.78; S, 10.93	Hg, — N, 4.68; S, 10.95

results indicated that bis-complexes were formed.

Thermogravimetric studies: Appropriate weights of the complexes were mixed with aluminium oxide and subjected to heating at the rate of 12° per min. The thermogravimetric curves showed that the thermal stability of the complexes are in the order Zn < Cd < Hg, the decomposition commenced at 95-100°, 110° and 135° respectively. The decomposition of the zinc complex became vigorous from 280° and finally a loss of 81.5% (calculated loss for conversion of ZnR₂ to ZnO, 81.7%) was recorded. Similarly, the rapid decomposition of the cadmium complex commenced at 215° and finally, a loss of 73.5% was recorded while the conversion of CdR₂ to CdO required 74.1%.

Effect of the concentration of the reagent : Approximately 100% and 75% excess of the theoretical quantity of the reagent was required for the quantitative precipitation of zinc and cadmium respectively at pH 7.0. But the mercury complex was completely precipitated at pH 1.8 when only a marginal excess of acetothioacetanilide was added. When more of the reagent was added the mercury(II) complex changed colour from yellow to greenish yellow though the weight remained unchanged.

Effect of pH : Zinc started precipitating at pH 5.2 and cadmium at 5.9 and the ranges for quantitative precipitation were 7.0-7.5 and 6.9-8.7 respectively. At higher pH the effect of hydrolysis was prominent. In case of mercury, the range of complete precipitation was pH 1.3-1.8. At lower pH there was a tendency of decomposition of the complex producing sulphide.

Effect of sequestering agents : Excepting borate and fluoride almost all common masking agents interfered in the determination of zinc. Cadmium was masked by cyanide, phosphate and disodium-EDTA, though the presence of citrate; tartrate, triethanolamine, salicylate, borate, fluoride and iodide showed no adverse effect. The precipitation of mercury was not marked by disodium-EDTA, tartrate or iodide.

Effect of diverse ions : The presence of AsO_3^{3-} did not interfere with the determination of zinc.

The quantitative precipitation of cadmium was possible from Al^{3+} , In^{3+} , Mg^{2+} , VO^{2+} and Cr^{3+} using 1 g of sodium potassium tartrate as the masking agent, while 1 g of citric acid was used when zinc was present. Triethanolamine masked lead. Mercury(II) may be precipitated at pH 1.5 and cadmium can be determined in the filtrate by the same reagent by raising the pH.

Several ions, e.g. Pb^{2+} , Mn^{2+} and Mg^{2+} did not interfere with the determination of Mercury(II) at pH 1.8, while Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Bi^{3+} , Fe^{3+} , Al^{3+} , Cr^{3+} , UO_2^{2+} , Th^{4+} , Zr^{4+} , MoO_4^{2-} , Sb^{3+} , Cu^{2+} , Ce^{4+} , VO^{2+} , VO_3^- , MoO_4^{2-} and TeO_4^{2-} had to be masked by sufficient $\text{Na}_2\text{-EDTA}$.

Determination of zinc in alloys : Several non-ferrous alloys were dissolved in hydrochloric acid and hydrogen peroxide and zinc was separated on an anion-exchanger. The process due to Gerdes and Rieman²⁸ was modified for the alloys concerned.

The mixture of the metal ions obtained by dissolving the alloys was passed through a column of 20-50 mesh Dowex 50-W-X8 (Cl^-) of 1.1 cm in height and 1.3 cm internal diameter. The column was washed with water and all other metal ions present (Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Pb^{2+} , Al^{3+}) were eluted with 10 ml of 0.5M hydrochloric acid. Zinc was subsequently eluted with 100 ml of 0.5M nitric acid and determined gravimetrically with acetothioacetanilide. A flow rate of 7 ml/min was maintained all through.

The experimental results are given in Table 4.

TABLE 4—DETERMINATION OF ZINC IN ALLOYS

Composition of the alloy (%)	Alloy taken (mg)	Zn found (mg)	Rel. error (%)
Zn 77.00	27.6	77.0	nil
Cu 22.92		77.1	+0.13
Zn 40.40	43.67	40.32	-0.19
Cu 56.50		40.30	-0.24
Pb 2.56	51.52	29.81	-0.06
Fe 0.10			
Zn 29.83	1.02, Al 1.38	29.89	+0.20
Cu 61.24, Sn 1.48			
Ni 2.15, Fe 1.50	1.30, P 0.05		
Pb			
Mn			

Precision and accuracy : The relative standard deviations were $\pm 0.5\%$, ± 0.31 and $\pm 0.14\%$ for zinc, cadmium and mercury(II) respectively. The confidence limits (95%) for the same are Zn, 16.36 ± 0.62 ; Cd, 2.39 ± 0.22 and Hg, 36.34 ± 0.10 .

Discussion

The mercury(II)-bis-acetothioacetanilide complex varied in colour from yellow to yellow-green depending on the temperature of drying though the weight remained unchanged. The thermal analysis curves with several samples were also identical.

When sodium or potassium chloride was added to enhance coagulation, the cadmium complex decomposed at $\sim 100^\circ$, but this temperature was $\sim 65^\circ$ when ammonium chloride was added though apparently the same complex was formed. The procedure for zinc will be of limited application but those for cadmium and mercury(II) are more accurate and selective than many existing methods.

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